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NEW INSIGHTS OF TRANSUNGUAL DELIVERY OF PHYTOCONSTITUENTS LOADED NAIL LACQUER FOR THERAPY OF NAIL DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Microorganisms like bacteria, fungus, and dermatophytes can infect the nails and cause diseases including onychomycosis, paronychia, and leuconychia. Pain, redness, swelling of the nail folds, thickness of the nail plate, and separation of the nail folds and cuticles are the symptoms of this kind of nail infection. Oral and conventional topical therapies (ointment, gel, cream) are frequently used to treat certain nail diseases. The drawbacks of oral medicines include their toxicity and the possibility that conventional topical preparations may wash off, which results in less drug penetration into nails. The novel formulations, such as medicated nail lacquers intended for transungual drug administration for the efficient treatment of nail infections, should be used instead of these conventional formulations. Long term use of synthetic drug has side effects. Many of the phytoconstituents used today have been valued for their antimicrobial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects. Investigating phytoconstituents with antimicrobial, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory properties that can be used as active ingredients in medicated nail lacquers to treat nail infections is the main objective of the article.

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INTRODUCTION

The nail is an external body part that serves a variety of purposes, including protecting the tips of fingers and toes from injury. However, when certain microbes, such as dermatophytes, yeast, bacteria, and fungi, are exposed, the nail becomes infected and causes diseases like onychomycosis, leuconychia, and paronychia [1].

Although nail illnesses are not life-threatening, they can be extremely painful, cause discomfort when performing daily tasks, and may have a major negative impact on a person's physical, mental, and emotional health as well as their quality of life [2]. Human nails do not have only a protective and decorative role, but can also be considered as an alternative pathway for drug delivery, especially in nail diseases such as onychomycosis, paronychia, psoriasis. These nail diseases are widely spread in the population, particularly among elderly and immune-compromised patients [3].

Oral treatment is often utilized to treat such nail diseases. The potency of medications decreases at the site of action when administered orally or systemically. Topical routes of delivery are utilized to prevent this loss of medication efficacy [1]. Topical drug delivery system is better as compared to oral drug delivery because of less systemic side effects, non-invasiveness, improved patient compliance, localized action (site-specific action) and possibly reduced cost of treatment [4, 5]. Ointments, creams, gels, lotions, and powders are examples of topical formulations that are commonly used in dermatology but are not appropriate for transungual administration. Such formulations are easily eliminated by washing or rubbing after application, resulting in non-uniform medication release. New topical formulations are suggested as an alternative to traditional formulations. Medicated nail lacquers are the best formulations. By adding rate-controlling polymers, the cosmetic nail lacquers are modified to create the medicated nail lacquers. As a film forms a reservoir of the medicinal material in the affected nail plate, this technique is thought to be effective for treating nail diseases [6]. This allows for less frequent administrations, and the active ingredients high bioavailability results in successful therapy. A film on the nail plate surface serves as a depot for the active ingredient and promotes optimal and continuous medication diffusion. Constant penetration of the active ingredient results in the therapeutic concentrations needed for the efficient treatment of nail disorders in the nail tissues [7].

These Nail lacquers formulations contain drugs to cure topical diseases; pharmaceutically they are called a Transungual drug delivery system. In the term Transungual, "Trans" signifies "through" and "unguis" signifies "nails" [5]. Transungual drug delivery is referred to as a method for delivering medication into the nail plate (Keratinized) in order to achieve targeted drug delivery for the treatment of nail disorders. Because of its greater adherence, localized action, and little systemic adverse effects, transungual drug delivery system is regarded to be extremely successful at managing nail disorders [8].

ANATOMY OF NAIL

The anatomy, physiology, and obstacles of the nail play a significant role in the improvement of nail medication delivery or successful transport of pharmaceutical components via the nail. A distinguishing feature of the human body is the nail, which is a horn-like membrane that covers the tips of fingers and toes [4]. The human nail is composed of many parts like nail plate, nail bed, matrix, nail cuticle, eponychium, hyponychium, specialized ligaments and nail folds.

1. **Nail plate:** The plate of the nail is the most visible portion of the nail apparatus. The nail plate is thin (0.25–0.6 mm), It is made up of translucent keratin protein composed of amino acids. It is hard, elastic, translucent and convex in shape and is mainly made up of 25 layers of flattened, dead, keratinized tightly bound cells [9].
2. **Nail bed:** The nail bed is made up of thin, soft epithelium that extends the whole length beneath the nail. It acts as a holder for the nail plate.
3. **Nail matrix:** It is a germinative epithelium responsible for the origination of nail plates. Nail matrix, also known as matrix unguis, onychostroma or germinal matrix.
4. **Nail fold:** It is mainly divided into proximal and lateral nail folds and the nail fold is mainly responsible for the protection of the nail against harmful agents, irritants, environmental pathogens [10, 11].
5. **Hyponychium:** It is the epithelium that is present below the nail plate between the junction of skin and the free edge of a fingertip. The main function of hyponychium is the formation of a sealer in order to protect the nail bed from an external microorganism.
6. **Paronychium:** It is also called the lateral nail fold which helps in keeping dirt, bacteria away from the nail. It is the soft tissue that surrounds both fingernails and toenails. It is responsible for the stability of the nail [4].

Because of its thickness and compact design, the nail's morphology acts as a barrier to the entry of topically applied substances. Drugs can permeate more easily through nails by disrupting the disulfide bonds in keratin [1]. Now, scientists are concentrating on modifying the nail plate barrier for efficient transungual delivery by utilizing the following techniques ;

- ❖ Chemical treatments as like use of various chemical penetration enhancers (sulfites, mercaptans, hydrogen peroxides, urea, water, Keratolytic enzymes)
- ❖ Physical techniques like (Iontophoresis, acid etching, carbon dioxide laser, hydration and occlusion, electroporation, UV-light, photodynamic therapy, sonophoresis / phonophoresis)
- ❖ Mechanical means like (nail avulsion and nail abrasion) for drug penetration [12].

Fig 1- Anatomy of human nail.

NAIL DISEASES

Diseases of the nails vary from pigmentation or discoloration to painful and debilitating states leading to atrophy, inflammation and brittle split nails. Nail diseases are shown in below Table.

Nail disorders	Features
1. Onychomycosis	It is Caused by dermatophytes, yeasts or molds. It may involve any component of the nail unit, namely the nail plate, the nail bed, and the nail matrix. Clinically onychomycosis presents with discoloration, thickening and irregular surface. Risk factors for nail infection are diabetes, age, smoking, compromised immune system Such as in HIV and peripheral vascular disease [13, 14].
2. Nail psoriasis	Nail psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory disease. The common symptoms of psoriatic nail are pitting, onycholysis, discoloration, subungual hyperkeratosis. It occurs approximately 50% of the skin psoriatic patients. [15, 16]
3. Paronychia	Paronychia is a bacterial, fungal and viral infection to nail folds and it occurs locally or superficially. This type of infection is characterized by pain, redness, swelling of the nail folds, thickening of the nail plate, discoloration of nail occurs and the separation of nail folds and cuticles. The Causative organism of paronychia is mainly, <i>staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>herpes simplex virus</i> . The infection can start suddenly which is Acute paronychia or gradually which is Chronic paronychia [11, 14].
4. Onychogryposis	It is also termed as onychauxis. This type of disease characterized by a thickened nail plate, trauma, nailplate will curve inward, pinching the nail bed and Colour changes to yellow- brown shade in nail plate [17, 18].
5. Tinea unguis	It is the nail ringworm and is characterized by deformity, thickening of the nail, and ultimately resulting in nail plate amputation [19].
6. Leuconychia	Appearance of white spots or lines on the nail caused due to trauma
7. Onychorrhexis	Brittle and rough nails which can easily be peeled or which often split vertically [14].

MEDICATED NAIL LACQUER AS TRANSUNGUAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

The conventional topical delivery systems have failed to improve nail adhesion and drug absorption due to the highly keratinized hydrophilic structure of nail which obstructs the passage of drugs. The surgical therapy systems are painful and invasive while systemic therapy produces serious side effects and a high degree of relapse. These issues have led to the advent of nail lacquers. Nail lacquers have an immense potential to improve nail adhesion as well as bioavailability. Nail lacquers containing drug are fairly new formulations and have been termed transungual delivery systems for treatment of nail infections [1].

Medicated nail lacquer provides the advantage of long duration of contact between the nail and drug and therefore the effective concentration can be reached a desired site. These formulations comprise the drug to be administered and are organic solutions of a film-forming polymer. Upon application the solvent evaporates, leaving a water resistant polymer film containing drug onto the nail plate. This occlusive film acts as a drug reservoir from which drug is slowly released and penetrates into and through the nail. Now a day, these formulations are used for the treatment of many nail disorders like onychomycosis, Psoriasis, Paronychia [20].

Mechanism of film formation and permeation

The nail lacquer acts as a film forming system which when applied to the nail or skin forms a thin and transparent film after the solvent gets evaporated. Drug penetrates through the nail plate is done by breaking disulphide bonds present in nail plate. It develops pore formation which allows a path for the drug to travel through.

The polymer film containing drug may be regarded as a matrix-type (monolithic) controlled release system where the drug is intimately mixed (dissolved or dispersed) with the polymer. It is assumed that dispersed drug will dissolve in the polymer film before it is released. Nail lacquer works by the mechanism of diffusion. Drug release from the film will be governed by Fick's law of diffusion, i.e. the flux (J), across a plane surface of unit area will be given by:

$$J = -D \frac{dc}{dx}$$

Where;

D = diffusion coefficient of the drug in the film,

dc / dx = concentration gradient of the drug across the diffusion path of dx [4, 21].

Fig 2 - Mechanism of film formation and permeation.

MARKETED NAIL LACQUER FORMULATION

In 1992, first medicated nail paint was introduced named as Loceryl®, which was formulated by the use of amorolfine 5% as drug including with other ingredients like ethanol, Eudragit RL 100, ethyl acetate, glycol triacetate. In 1999, FDA accepted Penlac®. Appearance of this nail lacquer was found clear and colourless liquid. It was formulated using ciclopirox 8% with butylmonester of maleic acid, ethyl acetate. Table 2 summarises a variety of nail lacquer based marketed formulation [2, 22].

Marketed nail lacquers

Name of product	Name of drug	Indication	Manufacturer
Loceryl	Amorolfine 5%	Onychomycosis	Roche laboratories, Australia.
Penlac	Ciclopiroxamine 8%	Onychomycosis	Dermil laboratories, Canada.
Loprox	Ciclopirox	Onychomycosis	Avents pharma Ltd, Mumbai, India.
Econail	Econazole 5%	Onychomycosis	JSJ Pharmaceutical, Chaleston.

PHYTOCONSTITUENTS IN NAIL DISEASES

At the present various synthetic antifungal and antibacterial drugs are used to treatment of nail diseases such as onychomycosis, paronychia, etc. But long-term use of synthetic antimicrobial drug has side effects. Many of the phytoconstituents used today have been valued for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory effects. So phytoconstituents having antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties and that can be used as active ingredients for treatment of nail infections without any side effects. Based on literature survey, reports of the antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activity of phytoconstituents are summarized in the following tables.

Table 3- Antibacterial and Antifungal activity of flavonoids.

COMPOUNDS	ORGANISM	MIC VALUE	REFERENCE
Quercetin	<i>S. aureus</i>	33 µg/ml	Alvarez, debattisa & pappano. 2008 [23].
Rutin	<i>S. aureus</i>	33 µg/ml	Alvarez, debattisa & pappano. 2008 [23].
Quercetin	<i>S. aureus</i>	20 µg/ml	Renu Narendra Jaisinghani.2017 [24].
Galangin	<i>S. aureus</i>	50 µg/ml	Cushine & lamb. 2006 [25].
Myricetin	<i>S. aureus</i>	50 µg/ml	Rashed et al., 2014 [26].
Galangin	MRSA	0.89-14.16 µg/ml	Pepeljnjak and Kosalec., 2004 [27].
Luteolin	<i>C. albicans</i>	37.5 µg/ml	Marina Sokovic et.al., 2020 [28].
Quercetin	<i>C. albicans</i>	75 µg/ml	Marina Sokovic et.al., 2020 [28].
Quercitrin	<i>C. albicans</i>	37.5 µg/ml	Marina Sokovic et.al., 2020 [28].
Rutin	<i>C. albicans</i>	37.5 µg/ml	Marina Sokovic et.al., 2020 [28].
Isoflavones (Daidzein)	<i>C. albicans</i>	516-1032 µg/ml	Lee, J.A.; Chee, H.Y., 2010 [29].
Isoflavones (Derrone)	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	7.81 µg/ml	Luc Verschaeve* et.al 2012 [30].
Isoflavane (Glabridin)	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>		
Rutin	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	6.3-12.5 µg/ml	Messier, C.; Epifano, F.; Genovese, S.; Grenier, D.,2011 [31].
	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>		
Quercitrin	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	256 µg/ml	Djouossi, M.G., 2015 [32].
	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>		
Quercetin	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	7.8-256 µg/ml	Djouossi, M.G., 2015 [32].
	<i>C. parapsilosis</i> ,		& Salazar-Aranda., 2015 [33].
	<i>T. rubrum</i>		
Quercetin	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	31.2- 125 µg/ml	Djouossi, M.G., 2015 [32].
	<i>C. parapsilosis</i> ,		& Salazar-Aranda., 2015 [33].
	<i>T. rubrum</i>		
Myricitrin	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	3.9-64 µg/ml	Djouossi, M.G., 2015 [32].
	<i>C. parapsilosis</i> ,		& Salazar-Aranda., 2015 [33].
	<i>T. rubrum</i>		
Galangin	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	15.6 -1000 µg/ml	Salazar-Aranda., 2015 [33].
	<i>T. rubrum</i>		& Bitencourt, T.A.; 2013 [34].
Kaempferol	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	31.2-512 µg/ml	Salazar-Aranda., 2015 [33].
	<i>C.parapsilosis</i> ,		
	<i>T. rubrum</i>		
Luteolin	<i>C.albicans</i> ,	3.9-83 µg/ml	Salazar-Aranda., 2015 [33].
	<i>C.parapsilosis</i> ,		
	<i>T. rubrum</i>		
Isoquercetin	<i>C.albicans</i> ,	2.5-5.0 µg/ml	Jose Realino de paula, Maria Do Rosario Rodrigues silva et.al., 2017 [35].
	<i>C.parapsilosis</i>		
Hesperetin	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	7.8-500 µg/ml	Vieira, M.L.A.; Johann, S.; Hughes, F.M.; Rosa, C.A.; Rosa, L.H., 2014 [36].
	<i>C. tropicalis</i> ,		
	<i>C. parapsilosis</i> ,		
Carvacrol	<i>C. albicans</i>	160 µg/ml	Zuzarte, M.; Vale-Silva, L.; Gonçalves, M.J.; Cavaleiro, C.; Vaz, S.; Canhoto, J.; Pinto, E.; Salgueiro, L., 2011 [37].
Dorsmanin	<i>C. albicans</i>	64 µg/ml	Armelle T Mbaveng* et.al., 2012 [38].
Epicatechin	<i>C. albicans</i>	25-250 µg/ml	Brighenti, Salvador, Gontijo et al. 2017 [39].
Apigenin	<i>C. parapsilosis</i> ,	5.0 µg/ml	Lee, H.;Woo, E.-R.; Lee, D.G., 2018 [40].
	<i>T. rubrum</i>		
Baicalin	<i>C.albicans</i> ,	250-500 µg/ml	Luc verschaeve* et.al 2012 [41].
	<i>C.parapsilosis</i>		
kaempferol	<i>s. aureus</i>	0.5 µg/ml	B. Ozcclik et.al 2006 [42].
kaempferol	<i>C. albicans</i> ,	25 µg/ml	Yordanov, M.; Dimitrova, P.; Patkar, S.; Saso, L.; Ivanovska, N. 2008 [43].
	<i>C. tropicalis</i> ,		
	<i>C. glabrata</i>		

Table 4- Antibacterial and Antifungal activity of alkaloids.

COMPOUNDS	ORGANISM	MIC VALUE	REFERENCE
Pellitorine (Amide alkaloids)	<i>S. aureus</i>	20 µg/ml	Srinivasa Reddy, P.; Jamil, K.; Madhusudhan, P.; Anjani, G. 2001 [44].
Piperlonguminine (Amide alkaloids)	<i>S. aureus</i>	12.5 µg/ml	Srinivasa Reddy, P.; Jamil, K.; Madhusudhan, P.; Anjani, G. 2001 [44].
β-carboline (Indole alkaloids)	<i>S. aureus</i>	8 µg/ml	O'Donnell, G.; Gibbons, 2007 [45].
koenigine	<i>C. albicans</i> , <i>C. tropicalis</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i>	12.5–100 µg/ml	Joshi, T et.al. 2018 [46].
Tryptanthrin	<i>T.mentagrophytes</i> <i>T. rubrum</i> ,	3.1µg/ml	Wang, Q* et.al. 2020 [47].
Piperine (Piperidine Alkaloids)	<i>S. aureus</i>	3.9µg/ml	Wang, J.; Wang, W.; Xiong, H.; Song, D.; Cao, X [48].
Tylophorinine, Tylophorinidine. (Phenanthroindolizidine Alkaloids)	<i>C. albicans</i> , <i>C. krusei</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i> ,	0.6-8 µg/ml	Xin, Z.; OuYang, Q.; Wan, C.; Che, J.; Li, L.; Chen, J.; Tao, N. 2019 [49].
Berberine	<i>C. tropicalis</i> , <i>C. albicans</i> , <i>C. parapsilosis</i>	8-16 µg/ml	Grangeiro, T.B.; et al.2016 [50].
Lycorine	<i>C. albicans</i>	39 µg/ml	Nair, J.J.; van Staden, J. 2018 [51].

Table 5- Antibacterial and Antifungal activity of Terpenoids.

COMPOUNDS	ORGANISM	MIC VALUE	REFERENCE
Borneol	<i>S. aureus</i>	0.03 mg/ ml	Cos, P.; Vlietinck, A.J.; Berghe, D.V.; Maes, L [52].
Camphor	<i>S. aureus</i>	0.015 mg/ ml	Cos, P.; Vlietinck, A.J.; Berghe, D.V.; Maes, L [52].
Borneol	<i>S. aureus</i>	5 mg/ml	W. Wang, Z. Ren, L. Wang, Y. Cai, Ma, L. Fang, J. Su 2021 [53].
Limonene	<i>S. aureus</i>	1 µg/ml	M.R. Zahi, M. El Hattab, H. Liang, Q. Yuan. 2017 [54].
Cymene	<i>S. aureus</i> <i>C. albicans</i>	15 & 3.75 µg/ml	Cutillas, A. Carrasco, R. Martinez-Gutierrez, V. Tomas, J. Tudela. 2017 [55].

Table 6- Anti-inflammatory activity of Flavonoids.

COMPOUNDS	MODE OF ACTION	CELLS/ USED	ANIMAL MODEL	REFERENCE
Quercetin	Cyclooxygenase-2 inhibition	Rat peritoneal macrophages		Serafini, M. 2010 [56].
Quercetin	Ob-Ra (leptin receptor), ERK1/2 phosphorylation, NF-κB, and TNF-α suppression	Leptin-induced human vein endothelial cells (HUVECS).	umbilical	Farzaei, M.H* et.al. 2019 [57].
Quercetin	Lysosomal enzyme reduction	Human leukocytes.	polymorphonuclear	García-Lafuente, A.; Guillamón, E.; Villares, A.; Rostagno, M.A.; Martínez, J.A. 2009[58].
Kaempferol	NF-κB inhibition	LPS treated macrophages		Serafini, M. 2010 [56].
Apigenin	Cyclooxygenase-2 inhibition	LPS treated macrophages		García-Lafuente, A.; Guillamón, E.; Villares, A.; Rostagno, M.A.; Martínez, J.A. 2009 [59].
Apigenin	NF-κB inhibition, TLR-4, Myeloid differentiation primary response 88 (MyD88), pI-κB-α reduction	LPS treated macrophages		Farzaei, M.H* et.al. 2019 [57].
Luteolin	TNF-α, IL-6 inhibition	IL-1-induced sarcoma cells (SW982)	human synovial	Choy, K.W.; Murugan, D.; Leong, X.-F.; Abas, R.; Alias, A.; Mustafa, M.R. 2019 [59].
Luteolin	NF-κB inhibition	Murine macrophages RAW 264.7		García-Lafuente, A.; Guillamón, E.; Villares, A.; Rostagno, M.A.;

Genistein	NF- κ B and Cyclooxygenase-2 inhibition.	LPS treated macrophages	Martínez, J.A. 2009 [58]. Serafini, M. 2010 [56]. & García-Lafuente, A.; Guillamón, E.; Villares, A.; Rostagno, M.A.; Martínez, J.A. 2009 [58].
Rutin	nuclear factor E2-related factor (Nrf) activation and NF- κ B inhibition.	Human embryonic kidney reporter cell line.	Farzaei, M.H* et.al. 2019 [57].
Fisetin	TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8 reduction.	Phorbol-12-myristate-13-acetate plus calcium ionophore (PMACI)-stimulated human mast cells.	Choy, K.W.; Murugan, D.; Leong, X.-F.; Abas, R.; Alias, A.; Mustafa, M.R. 2019 [59].

Table 7- Anti-inflammatory activity of Alkaloids.

COMPOUNDS	ASSAY	ORGANISM TESTED	DOSE	REFERENCE
Berbamine	In vivo, 5-HT-induced pedal edema.	Mouse	100 mg/Kg	Kupeli, E.; Kosar, M.; Yesilada, E.; Baser, K.H.C; Baser, C. 2002 [60].
Berberine	In vivo, carrageenan-induced pedal edema.	Mouse	2 mg/Kg	Yesilada, E.; Kupeli, E. 2002 [61].
Brucine	In vivo, carrageenan-induced pedal edema.	Rat	15 mg/Kg	Yin, W.; Wang, T.S.; Yin, F.Z. 2003 [62].
Decarine	In vivo, inhibitory activity on superoxide generation by human neutrophils.	Human	IC ₅₀ \leq 5.34 μ g/mL	Chen, J.J.; Chung, C.Y.; Hwang, T.L. 2009 [63].
Picrinine	In vivo, xylene-induced ear edema.	Mouse	10 mg/Kg	Shang, J.H.; Cai, X.H.; Feng, T.; Zhao, Y.L.; Wang, J.K.; Zhang, L.Y.; Yan, M.; Luo. 2010 [64].
Piperine	In vivo, intragastric.	Rat	20 mg/Kg	Daware, M.B.; Mujumdar, A.M. 2000 [65].
Scholaricine	In vitro, inhibitory activity on COX-1 & COX-2	Mice	100 μ M	Shang, J.H.; Cai, X.H.; Feng, T.; Zhao, Y.L.; Wang, J.K.; Zhang, L.Y.; Yan, M.; Luo. 2010 [64].

CONCLUSION

In this article, we just concluded that medicated nail lacquer proved to be a better tool as a drug delivery system for the transungual delivery of an drugs in the treatment of nail infections because of its good penetration and better adherence and when it is applied on the nail surface it leaves a thin film through which drug is released at the controlled rate to the site of infection. Despite treating the nail infections, the medicated nail lacquers can be also used for beautification of nails with ease of application. This improves patient compliance and acceptability. Based on this, this review identified and selected some Antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory phytoconstituents as the most promising active ingredients for use in the development of medicated nail lacquers for the treatment of nail infections without side effects.

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